

RESPONSE PAPER

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FIRST NAME: ZULU

PROGRAM CODE: LLM

COURSE CODE: ACA-401

PERIOD NUMBER: 1

INSTRUCTOR: GULMA

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

ACA-401 PERIOD ONE COURSEPACK

1) INTRODUCTION

Writing a thorough essay is essential to the success of any graduate student. There are several components and guidelines in achieving a solid paper in the academic world. “An academic essay aims to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence” (EUCLID 2019, 2). The basics consist of planning, researching, organization, drafting, referencing, editing and successful submission of a writing assignment. As well as, following proper guidelines for citation, plagiarism, mechanics, format, rules, and quotations. Having a clear knowledge on the process of writing a graduate level essay is imperative to a student’s academic success.

2) THE BASICS OF ESSAY WRITING

There are various steps in the creation of a good essay. In beginning an essay, utilizing good analytical skills to address the central point is imperative. It enables the writer to identify key concepts. “Analyzing, then answering the essay’s question or task is central” (ibid.). Another crucial step is researching and getting all necessary information to support the assignment. Get a grasp on what needs to be found out and locating the necessary sources to support your findings. “You must use evidence to support your argument, so look carefully for relevant information” (EUCLID 2019, 3). Gather this information by structuring notes and the sources in which they were attained. Once the necessary information to support the essay has been retrieved, it is essential to begin

organizing these notes and ideas. “Begin organizing your research and ideas into an answer” (ibid.).

Beginning the first draft is important to effectively approach the topic. Also, it helps to decipher which information or examples to be utilized throughout the paper. “Your first draft will not be your final essay; think of it as raw material you will refine through editing and redrafting” (EUCLID 2019, 4). While creating the first draft, focus should simultaneously be on the structure of the essay. The structure consists of the introduction, body and conclusion. The introduction allows the writer to introduce the topic and give a general idea of the contents of the paper. The body consist of paragraphs of information that present the topics, the supporting evidence and provide examples to the reader. The conclusion summarizes the main points and is very general. “However, NEVER introduce new information or ideas in the conclusion- its purpose is to round off your essay by summing it up” (ibid.).

In completing the essay process, there are a few more steps. Acknowledging the resources correctly by citing them is imperative. This process prevents any form of plagiarism. “Referencing guards against plagiarism, a serious academic offence” (EUCLID 2019, 5). Afterwards, edit the essay for any errors, revisions needed and anything that may have been overlooked. This step enables the writer to review any academic guidelines in formatting the essay and if all things seem seamless and balanced. “It’s important to READ the assignment guidelines in your course outlines and to follow them, find out how your lecturer/tutor would like assignments presented, and make sure you comply with their requirements” (ibid.). Lastly, is the final submission of the assignment. This step assures that the essay has been perfected, follows all criteria and concepts and is ready to be reviewed by the instructor.

3) REFERENCES

The essay writing process upholds strict rules in citing references and resources. When using quotes and paraphrasing an author’s work, EUCLID guidelines requires in-text citations. “When you cite something in the text of your paper, you simply need only to put the authors name in parenthesis with the page number that the information came from” (EUCLID 2019, 17). To be clear, paraphrasing is changing the words of the author’s work into your own words. Whereas, quotations are using the exact words from a published work.

The last page of an essay should contain a list of all works cited known as a bibliography. “It provides publication information for each of the sources that was cited in the paper” (EUCLID 2019, 33). There is precise format in completing a bibliography. The types of published resources range from websites, journals, videos and dissertations. A typical book format should be structured as follows:

Authors Name. Book Title. (Place of Publication: Publisher, Date)

For example:

Gerson, Steven. Technical Communication Process and Product. (Upper Saddle River: Pearson, 2009)” (EUCLID 2019, 34).

Plagiarism is the result of not properly acknowledging a published work within your essay. There are two clear forms of plagiarism.

First, you plagiarize when you use the words of a source without quotation marks. Second, you plagiarize if you take ideas from a source without footnoting the source. Sanctions for plagiarism depend on its severity and may range from lower grades on an assignment to a failing grade for the course (EUCLID 2019, 44-45).

4) EUCLID GUIDELINES

The EUCLID guidelines create a standard for all graduate students enrolled to adhere to a standardized formatting when submitting assignments. The general rules of writing mechanics apply to all essay submission. This entails the proper use of punctuations, grammar, spelling and capitalization. As well as a style guide to navigate the formatting and writing style within an essay.

The general rules of mechanics have a wide array of components. Proper comma usage is essential. “To join two independent clauses, use a comma followed by a conjunction, a semicolon alone, or a semicolon followed by a sentence modifier” (EUCLID 2019, 46). And it should be cautioned when utilizing nonrestrictive phrases and introductory phrases. Another common punctuation is apostrophes to typically show possession. “To indicate possession, end a singular noun with an apostrophe followed by an “s”. Otherwise, the noun’s form seems plural” (ibid.).

Consistency is achieved when complying with a style guide. Style guides allow “a need to ensure that the writing style is consistent and so guidelines are usually published to allow more than one author to contribute while ensuring that the finished piece does not necessarily carry the personal style of the writer but that of the publication, company or website associated with the writing” (EUCLID 2019, 52). Chicago Turabian format is the preferable writing style for essays at the graduate level. “Euclid recommends the Chicago Rules (Turabian), but other internationally recognized Rules are fine” (ibid.). Following a style guide allows for the writer to seek a reliable template to guide them through the writing process. It covers various forms such as a simple layout, fonts, paragraph structure, spacing, and other concepts.

5) AMERICAN AND BRITISH ENGLISH

American and UK English vary and have a slight difference and have various styles which reflect societal values. “Most divergence can be ascribed to differing national histories and cultural development, and the way in which the two national variants have changed correspondingly” (EUCLID 2019, 54). There are differences in concepts and mechanics such as spelling, punctuations, word meanings, grammar and expressions. In

understanding the differences amongst the two versions of English, it makes it easier to understand any cultural or historical barriers.

The writing mechanics vary between American and British English. The pronunciation and spelling for certain words can seem more complex. For instance, axe and ax, color and colour, check and cheque, maneuver and manoeuvre (ibid.). Even in the use of syntax rules within the both countries, there are slight differences such as EUCLID (2019, 55):

(U.S.) Finnair has a flight to London today

(U.K.) Finnair have a flight today

(U.S.) England has played well today, even if it lost

(U.K.) England have played well today, even if they lost

There are also differences amongst pluralized adjectives and its usage. For instance (ibid.):

(U.S.) John failed his drug test and will be excluded from the team

(U.K.) John failed his drugs test and will be excluded from the team

(U.S.) I purchased my new sandals from the shoe store on Mombasa Road

(U.K.) I purchased my new sandals from the shoes store on Mombasa Road

As for differences amongst expressions between America and England, there are various meanings and connotations that can be observed. In America, we may say that we need to ‘rent a car’ but in British English they may say ‘hire a car’ (EUCLID 2019, 56). References to colleagues and friends may vary as well. In America, we refer to companions as ‘friends’ and, in England, they refer to friends as ‘mates’ and ‘lads’ (ibid.).

6) CONCLUSION

Understanding the basics and various styles of writing an essay is key to our own success. Being cognizant of the various steps in creating an essay makes the writing process easier. Along with the process, there are several rules of mechanics, punctuation, quotation usage and grammar that must be adhered to. Following a specific writing style gives the author a clearer expectation of the consistency and flow of their work. It makes the information and argument to be made a more seamless process. What I was intrigued by is the differences between American and British English; from the mechanics, expressions, punctuations and syntax rules. As a graduate student, having a clear understanding of the EUCLID guidelines is important to my success in my essay submissions. Having a clear understanding of the steps, rules and content of creating a perfect essay accounts towards our own personal success in the pursuit of our endeavors.

REFERENCES

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